

Postpartum Depression and Intersectionality in Damilola Orimogunje's *For Maria Egun Pataki*

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Abstract

It is the nature of film everywhere to create its universe from the world around it. Nollywood has achieved a remarkable measure in this regard. One significant area is in the representation of mental health issues and postpartum depression (PPD) specifically. For Maria Egun Pataki stands out among other Nollywood films for the manner in which it has deployed and exploited postpartum depression in its thematic horizons. Using purposive sampling, the film is analysed through a close textual and extratextual reading. The theoretical framework adopted is framing theory within the broad context of intersectionality. Major finds include: For Maria Egun Pataki is a family drama oriented towards mental health issues/PPD from a purely non-conventional approach. The film frames how gender, culture and social stratification intersect to shape women's experiences of postpartum depression. Postpartum depression is validated as a legitimate medical and social issue. The film reflects cultural misunderstandings and handicaps about postpartum depression and its victims. The advocacy potential of the film is great.

Keywords: Postpartum depression, Nollywood, intersectionality, framing

Introduction

Nollywood, as the central and authentic voice in African cinema, has become a powerful platform for storytelling that reflects the social and cultural realities of African life. As one of the largest film industries in the world, it explores various themes, including themes of identity, family, and gender. Scholars have argued that Nollywood portrays the quintessential African society, which enables local viewers to see themselves and their communities more clearly and in real time as script writers and directors seem to pluck out stories from the everyday life of the people. This engagement with the local is crucial, especially when representing issues around gender and motherhood, because it often draws attention to struggles that are rarely spoken about openly.

Postpartum depression (PPD) is one of these hidden struggles in film, a theme that often occurs in many of the films as narrative slippages. They are part and parcel of the narrative unconscious, but they are nonetheless important because, as Karin Barber argues, like all

forms of popular arts in Africa, this theme means a lot to the people who consume them. Postpartum depression is a recognised issue in medical and psychological studies, but its representation in African cinema has been, to all intents and purposes, scanty. Existing research on mental health in African films often fails to account for the various factors that shape women's experiences.

Postpartum, frequently manifesting as depression, anxiety, psychosis, anorexia and weight loss, impacts millions of women worldwide. However, not all women experience postpartum depression in the same way. Identity markers like socioeconomic status, race, ethnicity, religion, and marital status shape these experiences. African women face added challenges due to cultural, social and economic pressures. These women face emotional and psychological difficulties after childbirth. They may experience these symptoms or simply feel overwhelmed in their new role as mothers. Yet, in Nigeria and other African societies, postpartum depression is rarely talked about. It remains a stigmatised topic. Postpartum depression is often seen as a personal burden – as that cross that is specifically designed for women. Consequently, mothers who suffer are often misunderstood and lack the support they need. Their experiences are shaped and further complicated by factors such as class, ethnicity, and religion.

Nollywood serves as a powerful medium for reflecting social values and struggles. Films often depict the complexities of womanhood, motherhood, and societal expectations. However, limited research has been conducted on how these films represent postpartum depression, particularly from an intersectional lens, which recognises how overlapping social categories create unique experiences of oppression or privilege. This study aims to interrogate how *For Maria Ebun Pataki* portrays postpartum depression through multiple social identities that shape a person's experience. Adopting intersectionality as a framework, this work answers the overarching questions: How is postpartum depression represented in the film *For Maria Ebun Pataki*? What intersectional indicators are prominent in the film *For Maria Ebun Pataki*? In what ways does *For Maria Ebun Pataki* challenge or reinforce societal stigmas surrounding mental health and motherhood?

Postpartum Depression

Postpartum depression is both a clinical condition and a social experience. Clinically, it is classified as a major depressive episode that begins during pregnancy or within four weeks

after delivery and in some cases twelve months after delivery (Gavin et al, 2005; Carlson et al, 2025). According to the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Health Disorders, fifth edition (DSM-5), postpartum depression is now included in the term perinatal depression.

Postpartum depression is a form of mental illness. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines postpartum depression as a disorder and a form of depression. Postpartum depression is one of the major health issues faced by women, even though a good number of cases go undiagnosed and untreated as a result of the lack of knowledge and awareness (Agrawal et al, 2022). The WHO reports that depression is a leading global cause of disability for all age groups and genders, but women experience higher lifetime rates of depression (10% - 25%) compared to men.

Globally, about 10-20% of mothers experience PPD (O'Hara and Wisner 2019). The numbers, however, vary widely. Studies show higher rates in developing countries, especially in areas marked by poverty, marital stress and poor health systems (Wang et al, 2021; Pan et al, 2024). Nigerian studies confirm this. Owoeye, Aina and Morakinyo (2006) found that about 23% of mothers are at risk in Lagos. Adeyomo et al (2020) found that the prevalence of postpartum depression in Lagos was 35.6% and identified both the obstetric and psychosocial predictors. In Bauchi State 43.4% prevalence of PPD, with its strongest predictors being family conflict and lack of spousal and family support during pregnancy (Mohammed et al, 2025). In Abeokuta, Sanni et al (2024) note that the prevalence of PPD was high (21.8%), occurring in one in every five mothers in the extended postpartum period. Factors associated with PPD as discovered are maternal age between 25-34 years, being married, and that perceived stress increased the odds of PPD. In Nsukka, prevalence was 20% with birth complications and poor partner support raising the risks (Anosike et al, 2024). Gombe and Owo show similar burdens, with social support emerging as a decisive protective factor (Laima et al, 2025; Tolulope et al, 2025).

The foregoing findings show that PPD is not marginalised in Nigeria. It is widespread. It is socially related and tied closely to family and community dynamics.

It is not clear what actually causes postpartum depression; however, it is believed that a combination of physical and emotional factors could be the cause. Corwin et al (2010) assert that, among other factors, PPD is a result of genetics. They opine that a woman's genotype

can determine whether she is likely to experience depression when faced with a common postpartum stressor. They highlight the complexity of PPD, which is susceptible to genetics, environmental factors and biological changes during the postpartum period (Corwin et al, 2010). To improve diagnosis and treatment, Corwin et al emphasise the necessity of an interdisciplinary approach to unravel these factors, which have lifelong implications for a woman.

The extreme consequence of untreated and prolonged PPD is evident in the case of Andrea Yates, who, in 2021, went viral on social media for drowning her five children. Even though it is presumed that PPD is a burden borne by women, its impact extends beyond the woman. Letourneau et al (2012) argue that it is not personal, as it does not only affect the mental health of mothers but also disrupts family dynamics. Postpartum depression manifests in social isolation, social support deficits, increased marital discord and reduced quality of maternal-infant interactions. All of which implies that the society is invariably affected by PPD. The effects of PPD are broad and interconnected, and sometimes could lead to societal costs; thus there is a need for comprehensive strategies in mental health care in order to mitigate these effects.

Mental Illness and Media Representation

Popular culture has contributed to the spread of mental health awareness. In Nigeria, this awareness has grown rapidly. The foray of conversations on the internet and social media has birthed an undeniable awareness of mental health. Although there are forms of mental illness, the most popular representation in film is madness. Perhaps, the oldest and foremost film (documentary) in Nigeria on madness is *Were Ni! He is a Madman* (1963) by Frank Speed, which documents traditional Nigerian/Yoruba treatments of mental illness.

In most cases, Nollywood portray mental illness stories as lopsided and stereotypical, contributing to the ignorance of mental illness. The portrayal of mental illness in the media has been explored by many authors, and they all agree that the media represent the victims in an inaccurate and unfavourable manner (Wahl, 1992, 1995, 2002; Harper, 2008, 2009; Whitley and Berry, 2013). Mental illness is portrayed as a cause of supernatural powers, including God and is deployed as poetic justice in films. This belief stems from the consciousness of Nigerians, who are highly religious. Common misconceptions that have continually been represented are the uncanny behaviour of mad characters in films. The

characters exhibit stock characteristics such as scary and outlandish behaviours, including murmuring, clapping their hands in a bid to kill an invisible fly, random bursts of laughter, and, in most cases, traces of violence and destruction.

In Nollywood, PPD is mostly framed within the context of real-life problems that manifest as risk factors, thereby ignoring the biological, psychological and environmental factors. Treatment narratives, as noted by Aroyewun-Adekomaiya and Aroyewun (2019), are mainly sourced in alternative medicine, including herbal treatment, exorcism and spiritual practices. This practice mirrors heavy reliance on the supernatural rather than on any form of psychiatric intervention. Because Nigerians are highly religious, such stories resonate with the audience. However, the implication is the looming danger and risk of perpetuating stigma and misinformation about mental health care.

Nollywood constantly portrays mental illness (PPD) from a moralistic perspective, employing poetic justice as a narrative technique to reward a character, thereby suggesting that personal shortcomings or external misfortune are responsible for mental illness (PPD).

Studies on the representation of postpartum depression (PPD) in Nollywood films are quite limited. Most works tend to focus on mental illness in general rather than specifically on PPD. This gap highlights an area this study aims to address because it provides a new perspective in an underexplored field.

Atilola and Olayiwola (2011) examined current frequency and modes of framing mental illness in the Yoruba genre of Nigerian home videos. Aroyewun-Adekomaiya and Aroyewun (2019) analysed the emergent themes and narratives in movies in order to explore the extent to which the media conveys mental health issues. More recently, Ayodele (2024) conducted a study that examines the depiction of women with postpartum depression in Nollywood films, the treatment methods and the perceptions of professionals in orthodox medicine, alternative medicine and the film industry on this portrayal.

While these studies undeniably provide valuable insights, they have not employed intersectionality as the basis for their analysis. This lack is what Postpartum Depression and Intersectionality in Damilola Orimogunje's *For Maria Egun Pataki* has endeavoured to address. Within the context of intersectionality, the study interrogates how factors like gender, social class, ethnicity, and religion intersect and overlap in influencing the experience of

PPD. This approach highlights the importance of this study in expanding the discourse around PPD and its media representation.

Methodology

The film text, *For Maria Ebum Pataki* by Damilola Orimogunje, was selected through purposive sampling. This selection was based on the film's thematic relevance in the portrayal of postpartum depression.

Purposive sampling is relevant to this research because it does not involve any kind of randomisation, which is common with quantitative research. This sampling technique enables the close reading of characters, themes, and scenes in the film under study.

For Maria Ebum Pataki is read as text. The close reading of the film involves the interrogation of the characters who drive the narrative, dialogues, visual style and cinematography that are used to foreground postpartum depression.

Theoretical Framework

This study employs framing theory within the broad context of intersectionality to elucidate and prop up the reading of *For Maria Ebum Pataki*.

Framing theory explains that the way information is presented influences how people understand, interpret and react to it. It was propounded by Erving Goffman in 1974 and was later refined by Robert Entman in 1993. The theory further explains how narratives select, highlight and organise meaning so that the audience interprets situations through a particular perspective. Entman (1993) proposes key functions of framing: problem definition, causal interpretation, moral evaluation and treatment recommendation.

In film analysis, framing actually goes beyond camera shots. It includes the entire storytelling process. It involves how the narratives are structured, how visuals are composed and how social issues are positioned within cultural discourse. This theory will yield a rewarding reading of the film *For Maria Ebum Pataki* (2020), especially against the context of intersectionality.

Intersectionality is used to foreground the idea that gender, culture, and socioeconomic status contribute to the experience of mothers suffering postpartum depression. Kimberle Crenshaw, in 1989, is known to have first introduced the metaphor of intersectionality as a framework

for understanding how multiple social categories (such as gender, class, and race) interact to create unique experiences of privilege and oppression. Although scholars have domesticated this concept in various disciplines, Crenshaw's intervention started as a legal critique of how the US antidiscrimination law failed to protect Black women from the overlapping harms of racism and sexism (Azmitia and Thomas, 2015).

When intersectionality is applied to film analysis, it helps to highlight how cinematic representations can either reinforce or challenge existing power structures and social hierarchies. In recent film scholarship, there has been increasing attention to how intersectionality can inform both the production and interpretation of films, especially those from marginalised communities. Herein lies the nexus between framing theory and intersectionality.

This approach recognises that characters' experiences are shaped by multiple identity markers that cannot be understood in isolation from one another.

The Originality of Concept, Storyline and Genre Experimentation in *For Maria Ebum Pataki*

The concept of the film comes across in the logline as carried on the Netflix platform: *After a complicated delivery, a mother struggles with postpartum depression and begins to withdraw from her family and the world around her.*

For Maria Ebum Pataki is a film directed by Damilola Orimogunje in 2020. The film is a departure from Nollywood's engagement with societal issues through its nuanced portrayal of postpartum depression (PPD) in Nigeria. The film follows Derin (Meg Otanwa), a new mother struggling with PPD.

The film opens with childbirth. Derin, the mother, is fighting for her life. It is a childbirth with complications; a traumatic childbirth. She eventually survives. The child is fine. But Derin is changed for life. The traumatic childbirth resulted in an emergency hysterectomy. Her womb had to be removed to save her life. She withdraws. She does not bond with her baby, Maria. She cannot. She struggles to breastfeed. Maria feeds on baby formula. Derin is weighed down by sadness and silence.

Her husband, Fola (Gabriel Afolayan), is helpful. He tries to understand her situation. But he becomes frustrated. Derin's mother-in-law, Grandma (Tina Mba), misinterprets her

behaviour. She sees Derin as unfit to be a mother. She expects her to rise and play the role of the perfect mother. Grandma resorts to praying. She believes it must be demonic for a mother to avoid her child.

Derin continues to experience other symptoms of PPD. She experiences bleeding gums and loss of hair, and ultimately, Tinnitus. She is diagnosed with extreme postpartum anxiety. Therapy is recommended, but Derin commits suicide before help could come.

The genre is family drama. The peculiarity here is the motif of postpartum depression.

In intent, content and execution, this film is centred on PPD. A closer reading, however, reveals that it has taken a step or two beyond this central concern. For it has added the additional weight of the loss of Derin's uterus. The point is this: remove the loss of the uterus, and the film would have lost virtually nothing. The only charitable interpretation of this inclusion is Nollywood's predilection to go beyond the mark.

Framing of Postpartum Depression in *For Maria Ebum Pataki*

The framing of PPD in *For Maria* is marked by the relatability of the narrative as well as the hysterical refusal to trivialise a potentially serious issue. Most Nollywood stories often glorify motherhood. They portray it as the crown on a woman's head: a woman's greatest achievement and feminine fulfilment. *For Maria* is a departure from the usual storyline. It portrays the emotional struggle that accompanies childbirth, a topic rarely spoken about.

The film portrays postpartum in a vivid manner. It makes the invisible side of postpartum visible. Away from the celebration of childbirth and motherhood, *For Maria* reframes motherhood in the context of PPD as a space of silence, vulnerability, and psychological struggle. PPD is shown not as madness but as sadness, exhaustion, withdrawal into self and silence. The narrative avoids exaggeration, the temptation of sacrificing depth for spectacle. It instead takes the audience on a journey of the intimate turmoil of Derin, a new mother, who battles postpartum depression. The film shows the following as indicators of postpartum:

- Unkempt appearance
- Emotional withdrawal
- Inability to bond with her baby
- Irritability, anxiety and silence
- Loss of interest in daily life

- Low mood/mood swings
- Fear of failure in motherhood
- Withdrawal from family and friends
- Insomnia
- Consistent crying
- Suicidal
- Bleeding gums
- Hair loss

These indicators are expressively portrayed. Derin's body language speaks more than words could. The audience is not entertained but is made to suffer the depression with Derin. The film frames Derin's depression through silence, stillness and minimal dialogue. The mise en scene is minimal; but not minimalist. No polish setting that distracts the audience from the thrust of the film.

The narrative highlights the society's inability to recognise PPD. Derin's mother-in-law, like many people in Nigerian society, interprets her detachment as ingratitude, unmotherliness, and a moral failing, rather than as a symptom of a medical condition. The film reflects PPD not as an individual failing but as a situation rendered more painful and agonising by society's refusal to acknowledge it.

The narrative structure is linear. It is deliberately not layered. It is scanty, allowing the full weight of PPD to be mirrored. The story is told in contained living spaces. A middle-class home. It shows the claustrophobia of Derin's experience. *For Maria* employs no subplots. The absence of subplots helps to keep the audience's attention focused on the protagonist's mental state. It puts PPD on a close-up, thus making it both the background and foreground of the story

Dialogue is sparse. It is minimal. Silence dominates the film. On the whole, actions and dialogue are interspaced with silence. The long silences create a rhythm that results in the slow pacing of the film. It also shows how time drags for someone in psychological distress. The film employs a slow pace to evoke empathy and position the audience not as observers but as participants in Derin's ordeal. The framing of time, space and character align with the

central thematic concern: the invisibility of postpartum depression in Nigerian cultural discourse.

Naturalistic cinematography reinforces the themes of depression, alienation and heaviness of the heart. There is no special technique employed in the lining up of the shots. More medium and close-up shots and less long shots have been lined up. The use of close-up and medium shots frames Derin as trapped within herself (Plate 1). The audience sees and feels the agony, the pain, the loss, and the emptiness she experiences. The long shots of her contained living spaces emphasise her isolation. She is consistently portrayed as bodily present but otherwise absent. She is surrounded by loved ones, but is invariably lost in her own solitude (Plate 2).

The lighting is dim. It is deliberately subdued. No bright colours. No shiny lights that flood the entire space. The lighting cast shadows; shadows that show Derin's state of mind. The cinematography avoids glamour and thus strips motherhood of its celebratory Nollywood gloss.

Sound design, too, plays a crucial role. Silence dominates, but is pulsated with the baby's cries that function as both a reminder of responsibility and a trigger for Derin's emotional unavailability.

Plate 1 Medium shot mirroring Derin's entrapment in herself (Source: *For Maria Ebun Pataki*)

Plate 1 Derin is only bodily present in the naming ceremony (Source: *For Maria Ebun Pataki*)

The visual style itself is a framing technique that compels the audience to perceive PPD not as spectacle but as a suffocating experience.

Intersectionality in the Framing

For Maria foregrounds how PPD is experienced at the intersection of multiple identities, such as gender, culture and social class.

Gender

Derin's depression cannot be separated from her gendered role as a Nigerian woman. Her identity as a woman in a patriarchal society places a great pressure on her to perform the roles of motherhood in a specific way—joyfully, sacrificially and without complaint. Motherhood is a cultural construct. It has been construed as the essence of womanhood; of femininity. Consequently, failure to embrace and express joy after childbirth is perceived as a moral failing. The film foregrounds this gendered burden by showing how Derin is judged against the cultural ideals of maternal responsibility. This is captured in the dialogue below:

Grandma: ...That is what a mother is called, doing things you don't want to do just for your children.

Nitori omo ni won se n pe ni "ABIYAMO",
O kan n k'era bai, o n gbe'ra soke, gbe'ra sodo, gbe jusile pete pete,
Lori omo kan niyen o, ti o ba wa bi omo ikeji nko? Ehn?
What if you have another child?

Derin: I'm not going to have any more children!
Grandma: Eh!

Grandma: ...That is what a mother is called. Doing things you don't want to do just for your children. They call women 'mothers' because of their kids. You are letting pain get the better of you. And you just have one child. What will happen when you have another baby? Heh? What if you have another child?

Derin: I'm not going to have any more children.

Grandma: What?

Although Grandma means well, she exemplifies the voice of uncomprehending tradition. Motherhood is accompanied by pain. Grandma says that the pain is normal. Derin's struggles highlight the gendered expectation that women must seamlessly transition into motherhood. Her failure to smoothly transition is judged harshly because she is a woman in a patriarchal society where maternal instinct is assumed to be natural.

Derin's silence and withdrawal become doubly coded: as both a symptom of depression and a refusal of the imposed gender script.

Culture

The film does not simply show PPD in a vacuum. It places it within a Yoruba-speaking household with strongly rooted traditional ideals. It situates it within a culture that glorifies suffering in motherhood and a family unit that lacks mental health literacy. This allows the film to explore why PPD is often invisible or misdiagnosed in Nigerian contexts—it is misunderstood, spiritualised, or simply ignored.

The story is told mainly in the Yoruba language. It leans into its cultural settings and exposes its flaws. The language adds authenticity, but at the same time emphasises the suffocating traditions that trap Derin. At its core, *For Maria* challenges a culture that celebrates childbirth but rarely attends to the mother's mind.

The naming ceremony represents another cultural dimension. In Nigeria, childbirth is a blessing, and it must be received with gratitude. The people are socialised to see childbirth as a communal celebration of life. In Yoruba culture, seven days after a child is born, there is a naming ceremony. The naming ceremony is often marked by rituals and the involvement of extended family and friends. During the ceremony, the child is given a name, Maria. This is

presumably where the film gets its titular title: *For Maria Egun Pataki*. The title literally translates in English as ‘For Maria, Special Gift.’ The baby is meant to be a precious gift. Children are gifts from God. But Maria is different. At least to Derin. Her birth is traumatic and filled with complications that lead to a hysterectomy, the removal of the uterus. Derin cannot remain the same again. She does not understand her body. She feels irritated. In her resentment, she changes the baby’s name from Salome to Maria. She had agreed on the name Salome with her husband, Fola. Salome is a Hebrew name which means peace. Maria, on the other hand, in Hebrew means bitterness. The baby does not bring peace into Derin’s home. So, Maria ironically becomes appropriate for a child whose arrival brings precisely these bitter emotional experiences for her mother.

At the ceremony, Derin refuses to participate in the celebration. Her refusal shows her as abnormal in the eyes of family members, whose dismissals reflect a broader cultural deafening silence of PPD. The film reframes this silence as not just individual but cultural—a product of collective denial. The intersection of culture and gender produces new levels of experiences: the shame Derin feels as a failed mother, and simultaneously being silenced as a woman whose psychological needs are subordinated to communal ideals of motherhood.

Another cultural dimension is in the fact that in Yoruba culture, it is the prerogative of the husband’s mother to attend to her son’s wife after birth (*omugwo*). This is regarded as a rare period of bonding between daughter-in-law and mother-in-law. Furthermore, it provides the unique opportunity for the mother-in-law to bond with her grandchild. The mother-in-law helps with domestic chores and takes care of the baby and the mother. In the film, Grandma judiciously lives up to the task. She feeds and cares for the baby. She persuades Derin to eat so that she can breastfeed the baby. Grandma is supportive. But she soon snaps when her efforts meet an adamant Derin, who is struggling with depression. Grandma insists that Derin’s case cannot be any different: she is not the first woman to go under the knife. For Grandma, what is happening to Derin is normal—Derin should brace up to the consequences of childbirth. When Derin demands that Grandma leave her home. Grandma does not put up a fight. She quietly leaves and, from the distance of her home, continues to play her caregiver role.

The film briefly highlights orthodox medication and remedies. Different people on different occasions offer different opinions on what Derin should do or should not. One week after birth, Derin has still not carried her baby nor breastfed her. The baby’s cry startles her. In

frustration, Grandma questions what kind of mother she is. She believes it is ridiculous not to carry or feed a baby you gave birth to. She insists that nothing is wrong with Derin. Nothing is wrong with her breasts. And that if she has issues with her breasts, she should say so that she can take *agbo*, an herbal concoction. The same concoction is also suggested by the stranger in the supermarket where Derin is shopping with her baby. The stranger believes that the reason Maria is crying profusely is because she has a stomachache and only *agbo* can cure her. During the naming ceremony, a woman advises that to recover quickly, Derin should sit in very hot water. A man also advised that the baby's head should always be covered to avoid air from entering her head. All these suggestions are from a place of care. It is a cultural thing. A belief that has seem to work for the people.

The concerns of friends, neighbours, and the community are rooted in the communal life of Nigerians. In our culture, a child is everybody's child. You may have given birth to the child, but the child is the community's child. Unlike the Western side of the world, where people mind their business, in Nigeria, communal living connotes that you become your brother's keeper. For instance, in the film, the couple's friends make it a duty to visit every week for a movie hangout just to support them. These concerns belong with the support system in the society.

Beyond its narrative, the film engages cultural discourse in significant ways. In a typical Nigerian society, discussions around mental health are often marginalised. Conditions like PPD are dismissed as merely mood swings, weakness or even laziness. The responses of Grandma reflect this cultural blind spot. She cares for Derin. She is supportive of her. But her inability to recognise or validate Derin's struggles represents the broader social reluctance to acknowledge PPD.

Traditionally, motherhood is idealised. A mother must be joyful. She must breastfeed without complaint and smile through exhaustion. Society scripts her role. But Derin fails woefully. She cannot act out this script. She is sad and detached. She resists breastfeeding. The film makes these visible. These moments clash with the cultural ideal of the 'good mother.' This shows how culture polices women, making private suffering a public offence.

Social Class

Although not explicitly shown like other factors, social class significantly shapes Derin's experience of PPD in the film. The couple are a middle-class family. They are an upward-

bound family. Fola is a professional. He has a white-collar job. Derin is a bespoke fashion designer. Husband and wife live comfortably. As a middle-class Nigerian woman, Derin has access to resources that would be unavailable to many others: hospital delivery, a comfortable home, and a husband who can take time off work to support her. Yet the film demonstrates how class privilege does not necessarily protect against PPD or guarantee appropriate care. Despite her relative privilege, Derin is the victim of a healthcare system that fails to provide adequate follow-up care or mental health support.

The film, through this, offers subtle commentary on the deficit in the healthcare infrastructure that fails to adequately cater for mental health needs in Nigeria. Although Derin is diagnosed with postpartum depression and is recommended for therapy, this intervention comes too late and is not actualised within the world of the film.

Challenging or Reinforcing Societal Stigmas on PPD

For Maria Ebum Pataki operates in a delicate space in this aspect. On the surface, it may seem as if it merely mirrors PPD: “This is what postpartum looks like.” But on a deeper note, it questions societal attitudes toward PPD and motherhood in Nigeria.

The film challenges stigma by portraying postpartum depression with nuance, empathy and medical recognition. It, at the same time, reflects prevailing societal silences. It shows how cultural expectations and ignorance reinforce the marginalisation of the victims of PPD.

The film disrupts the traditional way of telling mental health stories, which, in most cases, portray stereotypes of madness or moral failing. *For Maria*, instead, frames PPD differently through silence, stillness and emotional withdrawal. It does not tell the story in an exaggerated manner. It does not sensationalise the matter. The film presents PPD as a legitimate psychological condition. It avers in no uncertain terms: “It is okay if you suffer from PPD.” The approach of the film narrative adroitly compels the audience to empathise with Derin. By making PPD its primary focus, the film validates it as a real issue worthy of mention rather than a narrative afterthought.

Conclusion

For Maria Ebum Pataki represents a significant achievement in Nollywood films through its nuanced intersectional approach to postpartum depression. The film reframes motherhood as a terrain of vulnerability by its empathetic portrayal grounded in everyday realities.

Through an intersectional lens, the film emphasises how PPD is not experienced in isolation but is shaped by the interplay of gender, culture, class and religion rather than pathology alone. Derin's suffering is not simply personal but systemic: it is produced and sustained by patriarchal scripts of motherhood, cultural glorification of maternal sacrifice, inadequate healthcare structures, and the spiritualisation of PPD.

The film both challenges and reflects societal stigmas. It challenges by foregrounding PPD as legitimate and tragic.

While the film has limitations—abrupt ending and failure to explore treatment options—its overall achievement in projecting PPD in a relatable narrative is significant.

For Maria Ebum Pataki serves as a cultural discourse—one that broadens the discourse on postpartum and opens space for future Nollywood films to engage mental health with more empathy, accuracy and social consciousness.

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